

LOSS OF MEANING IN THE PROPHET: AN INTERCULTURAL PRAGMATIC PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

The cognitive studies on metaphor comprehension suggest that metaphors extend beyond their linguistic and conceptual functions to serve a communicative role. This study applies Steen's Deliberate Metaphor Theory (DMT) (2008), to analyze metaphors in *The Prophet* by Khalil Gibran and its Urdu translation. Grounded in intercultural pragmatics, the research examines the potential loss of meaning due to cultural differences between English (SL) and Urdu (TL). The analysis follows a three-dimensional model – linguistic, conceptual and communicative function of metaphors, as outlined in DMT. The study highlights how metaphor translation can impact meaning negotiation across cultural and linguistic boundaries.

INTRODUCTION

Translation of literary texts; texts that are driven by philosophical themes and meanings, is not an easy task because translation is a cultural communication that occurs between two different socio-cultural communication environments and not only a linguistic exercise. Furthermore, whatever is considered relevant in the source language context is not always relevant in the target language context hence, the translator's main job becomes the bridging of this gap. The translator takes the meaning and intention of one language and places it in another while trying to retain the source culture in the target culture without which the target audience would be at a loss. However, in order to reach that original intention, the translators may use different explicit efforts and effects as long as the implicit meaning is retained. (Huang & Wang, 2006)

In modern times, the understanding of translation has been a major concern of researchers as they consider it an important part of intercultural communication. With the advancement of pragmatics, which keeps context in the center and talks about utterances and interactions with regards to it – the scope of intercultural communication has broadened. Now it has been established that pragmatics plays a significant role in understanding translation phenomenon and that translation has a pragmatic perspective which needs to be further explored. Within pragmatics, the field of intercultural pragmatics has been widely growing and it is the only sub-field that studies the features of intercultural communication and merges them with pragmatics. The development and rise of intercultural pragmatics were important to

understand multilingualism that is now becoming a norm with globalization. (Kecskes, 2023)

Metaphors are now considered an important linguistic object in comparative investigations between source and target texts. Translation remains a difficult task with simple words but becomes a completely different process when it comes to understanding culturally specific words, idioms and metaphors i.e., words with different embedded concepts. The concept of metaphors has been of great concern for psychologists, linguists and philosophers over many years. Metaphor is understood to be a conceptual device that creates a relationship between language and thought. This rather new perspective opens door for its exploration in different fields related to translation, language, culture and literature. From a more cognitive point of view, it has found its footing in interdisciplinary research with translation studies, discourse analysis, education and now with cognitive poetics. If we look in detail, the concept of translation and metaphors appears to be very close – both come from Latin words referring to carrying the message across. Many attempts have been made to study methods, processes, and theories about the concept of metaphors and translation that create a connection between them. With this exploration it was revealed that metaphors by nature cannot be predicted hence translating them becomes an impossible task. However, instead of hastily rendering metaphors as untranslatable it was found that even though it is a problematic task it is still possible to convey their meaning through paraphrasing and explanation. (Degnev & Chervenкова, 2020)

When it comes to metaphor investigation and understanding the cultural differences between the source language (SL) and target language (TL), the difference between the source culture and the target culture becomes a hinderance in the translation process. According to (Lakoff and Johnson, 1980) metaphors are thought to be the objects used to make sense of reality and that structure the reality. Hence, the translators would have to be aware of both the source language culture and target language culture in order to convey the message in all its original essence. (Burmakona, E & Marugina, N, 2014)

Literary texts are considered the artifacts of language, philosophy and art, which together are used to convey meanings, feelings and emotions through the writer's intention. The language used in such texts is embedded with literal and figurative meanings essential in meaning-making and conveying the author's intention to the readers. Each piece of such text reflects the author's mind-set, life-experiences, and different takes on life. (Juden, 1994). This very quality of literary texts makes them a significant part of human life, especially when they are relatable. Every region has its own traditions and norms of producing literary texts through which they communicate with audiences and spread their culture. And since each writer has his/her own culture, we get variations in writing. (Wongkul, 1997) In ancient times, media was considered the only major source of artistic expression but today, it is established that art is not only a part of media or other fields related to it but also has its roots in literature, language, philosophy, etc. When it comes to writing, it is not only poetry that is considered art but also prose. A literary text then is defined as an artistic piece of writing conveying denotative and connotative meanings representing culture. This culture may be of individuals and/or regions comprising of their traditions, lifestyles, religions, beliefs, values, etc. Hence, while working with or simply reading literary texts we need to have basic culture awareness for comprehension. (Isariyawat, Yenphech & Intanoo, 2020)

In our daily communication, we tend to interact with people from our own context and language – whose language and linguistic choices are understandable because we are aware of the culture in which the language is used but also how the speakers use that language. In today's world, people want their culture to reach a wider audience and enhance its scope and seek relevance in broader contexts. In the case of a literary text, that reach is possible through translation. Translation is now defined as a skill and a complicated process of conveying meaning maintaining the essence of the original text. And to be able to achieve this the translator needs culture awareness of both the source language and the target language. This process of translation involves understanding, interpreting, and using the appropriate words that help in retaining the original

meaning and taking it to the target audience - which is not always a simple task given the complexity of texts and the availability of lexical items. (Mohemed & Akram, 2016)

Background

Khalil Gibran, a Lebanese American writer is known for his philosophical and spiritual writings. He is seen as a literary and political rebel, due to his unique expression and symbolist romantic style. Gibran belonged to a Maronite family and a Maronite school which highly influenced his interest in religion, Sufis and mysticism which are also central themes of his writings. The struggles of his homeland and the bloodshed that fills most of its history pages strengthened his belief in the unity of religions. Gibran's literary style is famous for using proper language and spiritual expressions. One of his most famous writings 'The Prophet' contains 26 poetic essays and got fame during the 1960s with the new cultural movements in America and still is popular today. It was then translated into twenty languages and was considered his most famous work. Gibran gives a view of the world through the eyes of a philosophical man who has a desire to make the world a better place and guide people towards a more positive and spiritual way of life. The ideas expressed in the book are more instructional and lead the way for anyone who is looking for a direction in finding light. The name of the book 'The prophet' means the chosen one in Arabic, it is one name amongst many names that maintains the connection with the Prophet Muhammed (PBUH). Which reflects that the choice was not random and was greatly influenced by Gibran's interest in Islam and other religions. Gibran's unique take on life, appealing expression, and interesting use of imagination - which most people could relate to and take inspiration from, made him popular worldwide. (Mohemed & Akram, 2016)

For an even wider reach of Gibran's work, many attempts at translating it in different languages were made. One such attempt was made by Habib Ashar Dehalvi in 1981 to translate the work into Urdu language. Dehalvi had attempted translations of most of Khalil Gibran's work including 'The Prophet' in Urdu language. He was a poet, born in Delhi in 1919 and was known for most of his poetic work related to different themes of life. In his own

words, the translator appreciated the importance of Gibran's most renowned work and considers his expressive style a unique one that stands out even today. His work is relatable and provides a different way of life to the readers and if nothing else it gives them food for thought - no one after reading 'The Prophet' would be left without the need to think and reflect. Ashar's translation was published by the name of 'Al Nabi' in 1977. (Dehalvi, 1977)

Problem Statement

Literary texts in general and poetry specifically, are enriched with metaphors and metaphorical meanings, which are comprehended easily if the readers are aware of the explicit and implicit meanings (context/culture) in the texts. However, it is when they are translated in another language to be presented to a target audience that the problem of retaining the original meaning occurs. Since, metaphors serve the communicative function and meaning is highly dependent on them especially in poetry, it is of utmost importance for the translators to carefully exhibit that communicative function in order to avoid distorting the original meanings. However, this is not always the case.

Research Objective

To analyze the function of deliberate metaphors in *The Prophet* in mediating the author's intended message in English (ST).

To examine the alterations in this mediation in Urdu (TT).

Research Question

How do the deliberate metaphors in *The Prophet* function to mediate the author's intended message in the ST, and how is this mediation altered in the TT?

Significance

The current research was conducted under the scope of intercultural pragmatics and within that under the perspective of Deliberate Metaphor Theory (Steen, 2008). This study is significant because of four reasons 1). It takes the DMT perspective which is a relatively newer perspective in metaphor analysis. 2). The DMT highlights the communicative function of metaphors and shifts the focus from just the lexical

units to the communicative (metaphorical/contextual/cultural) function. 3). The selected text is enriched with philosophical metaphors and talks about various cultural aspects that relate to human beings and genuine human emotion which proves to be a guiding light and gives people a direction to lead their lives. 4). The selected text and its translation have not been analyzed or studied from intercultural pragmatics perspective previously especially in the selected English (SL) and Urdu (TL) cultural contexts.

Deliberate Metaphor Theory

Within the cognitivist approach to metaphor, the comprehension of metaphorical statements or utterances is possible under two different views i.e., comparison and categorization. In the comparison view, we compare the metaphorical use of the words to their literal meaning therefore, mapping the two meanings across the literal and metaphorical domains. The interpreter has both the terms literal and metaphorical active in mind while comprehending the meaning of the metaphorical statement without which comprehension would not be possible. On the other hand, the categorization view considers the literal meaning as the prototype around which the metaphorical meaning works by blocking all the irrelevant features therefore, constructing meaning. Furthermore, metaphors have linguistic, conceptual and communicative properties where even though the linguistic and conceptual properties have been discussed in detail the communicative one has long been neglected. This communicative function is the main concern of Deliberate Metaphor Theory (DMT). In Deliberate Metaphor Theory, metaphors are not only considered conceptual structures (metaphor in thought) expressed in linguistic forms (metaphor in language) but also a significant part of communication between language users (metaphors in communication) – with a clear distinction between thoughts, words used to express those thoughts and the persons, places, things, actions, or events in the world that the words refer to. Hence, giving birth to a three-dimensional model. This theory divides metaphors into deliberate and non-deliberate metaphors w.r.t to the communicative function which is the main concern of this research.

When a metaphor is used deliberately it provides another perspective to the topic under discussion and urges the reader (interpreter) to move from what they know to how it could be. Which in turn takes the interpreter from the target domain to the source domain, that is not the case in non-deliberate metaphors. The deliberate metaphors are processed under comparison view and non-deliberate ones under categorization view. (Steen, 2008)

Deliberate metaphors are different from non-deliberate metaphors in such a way that the speaker (sender) wants the receiver to set up a cross mapping domain in their mental representation of the message that they are receiving. This makes the deliberate metaphor a very distinct and unique kind of metaphor that is not limited to just language or thought but expands over both. Based on this, there is a need for multilevel models to understand the use of metaphors in cross-cultural and intercultural communication. These multilevel models will help to see metaphors beyond their linguistic functions. The levels include linguistic, conceptual and communicative based on the functions performed by the metaphors. (Steen, 2008)

The main focus of this study will be on the communicative function (that refers to how speaker/writers communicate in order to create meaning and convey that meaning to an audience) of metaphors under the perspective of intercultural pragmatics to understand how metaphors create meaning and need to be understood carefully in order to be translated into another language.

Deliberate Metaphor Theory and Translation

Metaphor, a common feature of communication, has always been a challenge for readers when it comes to comprehension. It serves as a greater challenge for translators, who attempt to convey messages from one culture to another. According to (Schaffner, 2004), there are various methods that can be used to translate metaphors. These methods include substitution, deletion, and paraphrase and help in translating from different languages but in this case from English and German. The study focused mainly on how translators handle metaphors in political discourse of English and German languages, its effect on the overall text and future implications under the scope of Translation Studies.

A study conducted by Hidayatullah (2019), focused on the imagery that was used in Gibran's work by using Laurence Perrine's theoretical framework. He concluded that the imagery was used by the author to convey to the readers that life has a lot to offer, it is not just the desires and needs of human beings that could be considered the sole purpose of their existence and once they realize this, they need to start their journey in pursuit of the deeper meanings of life.

To further expand on how concepts are perceived in the cognition of the human mind, translation plays a vital role. A study conducted by Hong & Rosi (2021), focuses on the metaphorical structures of metaphors and their translation under the Conceptual Metaphor Theory. This study investigated the role of cognitive metaphors and how meaning is created through them especially in cross-cultural communication. The author took English-Chinese and French-Chinese translations and gave a critical view on how descriptive translation and interpretative theories of translations can work together in order to understand the communication process in multilingual contexts.

As we move further, we see that metaphors are not only used to express concepts but also through those concepts they help in creating and constructing identities and ideologies especially in literary texts. Vengadasmy (2016), studied two Malaysian short stories under Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT) and illustrated how the word *LAND* takes on a sociological view of ideology under the theme of nationhood. It was a cognitive approach that reflected on the structural mapping across the source and target domains in order to highlight the social and cultural beliefs of the author.

Metaphors have long been used to explain different social, political, linguistic and psychological realities. These realities within their respective areas are not limited to a single human identity or status. For instance, metaphors help in creating, constructing and developing the realities of marginalized communities, refugees, women, etc. and the discourses surrounding them. One such research conducted by (Mujagic & Berberovic, 2019) in order to understand the immigrant discourse in English and Bosnian/Serbian/Croatian languages took Deliberate Metaphor Theory (DMT) perspective to

study context in comparison to animals. The main question it answered was that how deliberate metaphors are used in media discourse to dehumanize immigrants and reduce the viewers' empathy for them.

From the above discussion, it is understood that metaphors and specifically deliberate metaphors provide a broader and multidisciplinary approach to comprehension of different world views. It is considered a very significant addition to cognitive approaches to metaphor comprehension. (Hassanein, 2022) provides an elaborate view on the gaps left behind by (Steen, 2008) DMT by representing the idea of vividness and lexical factors while keeping the socio-cultural and psychological background of the speakers (who use metaphors) in account. In this study (Hassanein, 2020) kept under consideration the speakers of English and Arabic languages. He concluded that in order to fully comprehend the deliberate and non-deliberate metaphors, the speakers socio-cultural and psychological background cannot be ignored as it plays an important role in deciding the use of deliberate or non-deliberate metaphors.

Methodology

The current study focuses on the relatively newer Deliberate Metaphor Theory proposed by (Steen, 2008) that highlights the communicative function of metaphors in language. From the theory a multilevel model is derived that consists of three levels namely: linguistic - that talks about the lexical choices of the author and the translators, conceptual - that explains the concept being conveyed through those lexical choices (metaphors) and communicative level - which describes the cultural aspect depicted in the metaphors and how it is distorted during the process of translation. On these three levels, the metaphors used in the selected text in English (source language SL) and its translation in Urdu (target language TL) will be analyzed, the metaphors are selected on the basis of the cultural meanings that they convey in the SL and to understand how meaning depends on the translator's exhibition of both the SL and TL cultures that serve the communicative function in each language. Based on this, four culturally driven poems are selected from a collection of 26 poems in 'the prophet' namely On Marriage, On Children, and On Clothes. The selected poems will be analyzed to

Deliberate Metaphors	
ST (English)	TT (Urdu)
You shall be together even in the silent memory of God.	کہ تک یہاں گے رہو ساتھ تم! ہاں میں حافظے گہمیر کہ اللہ بھی
Fill each other's cup but drink not from one cup	پیو نہ سے پیالے ہی ایک لیکن بھرو۔ پیالہ کا دوسرے ایک
Give one another of your bread but eat not from the same loaf.	نہ کر مل روٹی، ہی ایک دونوں لیکن دو، نوالہ اپنا اپنا کو دوسرے ایک کھاو۔
Let each one of you be alone.	رہو بھی آزاد سے دوسرے ایک
Give your hearts, but not into each other's keeping.	بناو نہ مالک اسے مگر دو کو دوسرے ایک دل اپنا
For only the hand of Life can contain your hearts.	سکتا رکھ میں قبضے کو دلوں تمہارے ہی حیات دست صرف کہ لئے س ہے۔
And stand together yet not too near together.	جاو۔ نہ چمٹ سے دوسرے ایک لیکن ہو، کھڑے ساتھ کہ دوسرے ایک

investigate how culture is embedded in the communicative function of metaphors and how meaning is lost due to the difference of metaphor use in the source and target languages.

Deliberate Metaphors and Loss of Meaning in 'The Prophet'

On Marriage

Marriage, in different cultures, is understood differently in terms of how married couples form their bonds. In the original text, the author has presented marriage as a very enriching concept that helps people grow together with each other and individually at the same time. So as to say that the presence of a life partner does not become a hindrance in the other person's growth. On the contrary, the translated text depicts an opposite view of the same concept and sometimes negates the idea that being together is healthy and brings prosperity in the couple's life. If we look at the lexical choices of both the author and the translator, we'll understand the difference between the culture of the SL and TL.

Lexical Level:

On the lexical level, in the source text the author has deliberately tried to create an image where he is conveying the message that humans share temporal space since birth, and they will remain together till the end of time. Especially when they get married - where marriage is a union of two souls who join and vow/enter a contract to build their lives, they'll be together even more. By using 'in the silent memory of God', he further implies that in this togetherness when you know that death could separate you, God also seems distant and there's a possibility of

separation because of it you need to have faith that God knows, and the higher power is aware of your existence and the relationship. Furthermore, the translator uses 'میں حافظے گہمیر' for 'silent memory' which has a completely different meaning in the TL and refers to the complexity of God's memory but not the metaphorical meaning behind it as the author had intended in the ST. Moreover, the translator's use of 'پیالے' refers to a concrete object in the TL which is contrary to the use of 'cup' in the ST. The word 'cup' is used metaphorically in the SL for soul, body, or existence, etc. that contradicts the literal use of 'پیالے' in the TL. the lexical choices of the translator 'کھاو نہ کر مل روٹی، ہی یک' talks about a more typical culture that is prevalent in society not only about couples but people in general.

The use of 'bread' by the poet is an indication to a broader concept of give and take in a relationship which 'روٹی' does not elaborate. Also, the use of 'alone' does not mean 'آزاد' as both these words have different meaning in their respective contexts - the former means to be yourself, have your individual interests intact and the latter means 'freedom' as if married people are not free to follow their individual paths when they are together and need to break free from each other literally. In addition to this, the use of 'give your hearts but not into each other's keeping' being replaced by 'دو کو دوسرے ایک دل اپنا' changes the meaning of how partners give each other their hearts - they love each other and feel safe enough to be vulnerable around and with each other but the use of 'مالک' means to give ownership of something to someone else. Just like 'قبضے' being used for 'contain' in the next excerpt, the former means to occupy and the latter

means that something willingly fits into something in this case, the hand of Life which is used metaphorically.

In the last excerpt, the author intends people to understand that couples should be close and be united, but that togetherness must not be suffocating for each of them which does not mean 'جاو- نہ چمٹ' as in the TT. Because each of these words refers to something completely different in meaning; being together is positive while 'چمٹ' is too clingy - which the author wants people to avoid doing in their relationships.

Conceptual Level:

The author had intended to take the readers to the broader aspect of invisible things - just because something is invisible does not mean it is non-existent. Which is distorted with the use of 'گھمبیر' in the TT. From the poet's choice in the ST, the excerpt points towards the married couple knowing that the relationship they are in and the whole concept of marriage is not supposed to be selfish. Each of them must not focus on only fulfilling his/her own needs but also consider the other person and their needs. However, with the use of 'بھرو پیالہ' and 'پیلے بی ایک' the whole concept becomes a reference to the culture of how people eat and drink, sometimes they share their food and even they drink/eat from the same utensil. This is a common practice in the SL and TL culture, where people might share their food and drinks.

The author in ST wanted the readers to understand that marriage is about sharing what each participant has to offer. In the SL culture, it is considered a relationship based on equal terms whereas, in the TL culture marriage traditionally is seen as a concept where two people have to share the material and do things together. Therefore, when the translator uses 'کھاو نہ کر مل روٹی، ہی یک' distorts the meaning and the connotation turns negative. As if the author is asking married couples not to sit and eat together. In the SL culture, the coming together of people especially the married couples mean to have common interests while keeping your individuality intact. However, 'زاد' in the TL culture means the wife or the husband can only be themselves when they are apart.

The author wants the readers to see marriage as a place where they can be themselves and have their own personalities without changing what matters the most to them - without having to change their passions, interests, what makes them happy or sorrowful, have their own dreams, etc. Couples share their sorrows, joys, happiness, the good and the bad, and yet they have their individual pursuits as well, for which they do not need to break away from their partner, instead they can be together and follow their dreams. The idea of not suffocating each other just because you are married completely changes in the TT.

Communicative Level:

At this level, in the TL the use of 'اللہ' refers to a certain religious and cultural aspect and narrows down the broader concept that was expressed in the SL. In the SL, the author does not only mean that people of a certain culture - Muslims, are the only ones who need to have this faith or belief that there's a higher power that has a role in their life and whatever they do. Hence, this distorts the overall meaning of the text.

From the difference in the lexical choices of both the author and the translator, the whole meaning is distorted and there is the loss of culture - the author wanted the readers to take a lesson and create a culture of care and understanding among the married couples, their consideration of each other's needs and individuality. However, in the TL, the whole concept narrows down to the mere practice of sharing food because of the lexical choices and the more literal use of words. We understand the use of 'cup' was deliberate in their context of use in the ST and overall it was the deliberate metaphors that have been distorted in the TT. Due to the difference in the lexical choices of the author and the translator, the culture gets distorted since the meaning that TT conveys is not what the author had intended in the ST.

The author had used deliberate metaphors to symbolize that married couples need to share, there is a give and take in their relationship. However, the translator narrowed the broader concept of sharing and brought it to mean that the partners need not share and eat their own food. The author wanted the readers to see marriage as a coming together of two

individuals who are free to breathe and be themselves while being together and supporting each other. The translator, however, makes the TT adapt to what is a norm in the TL culture – the people who speak Urdu (belonging to India and Pakistan mostly) see marriage from a very different perspective, they do mostly see marriage as owning of another person

and trying to govern their actions which is almost completely opposite to how it is practiced in the SL culture. Hence, the intention of the author is distorted; the culture he wanted people to practice in their married lives and therefore, the original meaning is lost.

On Children

Deliberate Metaphors

ST (English)	TT(Urdu)
They are the sons and daughters of Life's longing for itself.	ہیں بیٹیاں اور بیٹے کے زندگی وہ
For their souls dwell in the house of to-morrow	ہیں۔ رہتی میں گھر کے مستقبل روہیں کی ان
Which you cannot visit, not even in your dreams.	سکتے۔ جا نہیں تم میں گھر اس سکتے دیکھ نہیں اسے بھی میں خواب اپنے
The archer sees the mark upon the path of the infinite.	لگتا پر رستے کے ابدیت جو ہے دیکھتا کو نشانے اس اللہ اور ہے۔
And He bends you with His might that His arrows may go swift and far.	ہے۔ کھینچتا کو کمانوں ان سے قوت اپنی اللہ جائیں۔ دور بہت اور تیز بہت تیر کے اس تاکہ
Let your bending in the Archer's hand be for gladness.	جاو۔ جھک سامنے اس کے خوشی خوشی تم پس
For even as He loves the arrow that flies, so He loves also the bow that is stable.	ہے۔ کرتا محبت سے تیر ہوئے اڑتے وہ طرح جس کہ لئیے اس ہے۔ رکھتا عزیز بھی کو کمان مضبوط وہ طرح اسی

Children, as typically understood to be either sons or daughters, are not meant to be only identified as that according to the author. In the original text, the author wants people to understand that even though parents do give birth to their children, they are to be nourished and brought up with care. Parents do not own their children and cannot dictate their minds to follow what they want them to follow in life. They need to provide them with a solid foundation while also letting them fly and move independently in the world.

Lexical Level:

In the ST, the use of 'sons and daughters of Life's longing for itself' refers to how life is not owned by the parents but the One who gave them this life. The use of 'house of tomorrow' does not mean a literal house with walls and a ceiling, and where people are confined in one space, however, the use of 'مستقبل کے گھر' refers to a literal house in the future. And which the parents cannot 'visit' even in their dreams – a culture of visiting people's houses to meet them. The use of 'اللہ' again distorts the meaning of 'archer' who sees the mark upon the path and 'He bends you with

His might' – it is not just the blending of two cultures but also the distortion of both. The idea of bending in front of the archer is different from how believers bend in front of 'اللہ' in their contexts. Furthermore, the word 'stable' means to have a strong foundation, not a rigid one which is not what 'مضبوط' means in the TL.

Conceptual Level:

The source text revolves around the broader aspect of having children, which is that the parents should not consider them their property. The children are given birth to by the parents, but the life that is given to them needs to be explored by them in their own way. The parents must not dictate them or try to influence their thoughts while considering them their puppets. In the TL culture, parents see their children as their belongings, and because of their traditions, they want their sons and daughters to inhabit the norms and become what society demands them to become. However, the almighty who has given them life gives them the freedom to think independently, be loved and nourished by their parents and be independent in pursuing their

dreams while keeping a strong connection with their roots. The translator, through his lexical choices, distorts the meaning of the original and limits the idea of souls roaming freely and building their future to 'گھر' and mixes the cultures of the how the archer sees arrows and how 'الله' sees his creation.

Communicative Level:

As mentioned above, the cultures in the given excerpts of the TT are distorted in such a way that the metaphorical use of 'sons and daughters' and 'house' limits the imagination of the readers of the TT. They are made to think that the culture they are

familiar with is being referred to in the ST, which is not the case. The author had intended the readers to understand that as parents they need to let their children live their lives independently even when the children live close to them, they should have the freedom to think independently. This is how they would be able to build their future and be happy in God's will. To please 'the archer', they need to take the pain of restraint and letting their children be - once that happens the children would be able to go far in life while also having their strong connection with the parents which would not be because of the biology only.

On Clothes

Deliberate Metaphors

ST(English)	TT(Urdu)
For the breath of life is in the sunlight and the hand of life is in the wind.	اور ہیں ہوتے میں کرنوں کی سورج سانس کے زندگی کہ لئے اس ہیں۔ کرتے حرکت ساتھ کے ہواوں ہاتھ کے زندگی
It is the north wind who has woven the clothes we wear.	ہیں۔ ہوئے بنے کے شمال باد وہ ہیں پہنتے ہم کپڑے جو
And when the unclean shall be no more, what were modesty but a fetter and fouling of the mind?	ایک سوائے ہے، جاتی رہ کیا شرم تو رہے نہ ہی بدکاری جب اور ہے۔ دیتی بنا ناکارہ کر باندھ کو عقل جو کے زنجیر
The wind longs to play with your hair.	ہوئے برساتے نغمے سے منہ کے اس سانس کے شغف و شوق ہیں۔ لگتے نکلنے

Clothes are understood to be the source of cover and protection from the cold and other elements. In some cultures, they are considered a symbol of modesty and privacy. In literal terms, clothes also hide the beauty of the human body and shield the skin from the sun and eyes of the unclean. It is thought that clothes become a hindrance in the natural world - the natural part should not be hidden when there is nothing to be afraid of.

Lexical Level:

In the SL culture, clothes are presented as the expression of the inner self, chosen without any fear and thought of the external elements. However, in the TL 'انس کے زندگی' used for the 'the breath of life' shatters the idea of the beauty that the life holds and the innocence and freedom it brings. It is not a literal phenomenon that breathes like a human being and works like one too. The idea of 'north wind' also has a different connotation than 'شمال باد' in the TL. The north wind again has been personified as if the wind sits and sews/knits the clothes that we wear. Moreover, 'ایک سوائے کے زنجیر ایک سوائے کے

ہے refers to a chain that may turn the mind numb and it stops working if there's no concept of 'the evil/unclean eye' remaining in the world as depicted in the TL. But this depicted is a distortion of the original meaning, which is raised as a question by the author, that if there's no unclean eye left in the word, what would then be the use of modesty, that the translator has presented as a fact. And finally, the use of 'منہ سے نغمے ہوئے برساتے نغمے' in place of 'the wind longs to play with your hair' paints a very different picture than in the ST. Because longs to play does not mean 'منہ سے نغمے ہوئے برساتے نغمے' in the SL, the latter refers to singing songs while the former is about a longing - a desire and is said metaphorically.

Conceptual Level:

In different cultures, north wind has literal and figurative meanings, in the broader sense of the word it means the cold wind that blows due to our harsh climates and in the context of this poem it means that the evil eye or an unclean eye that looks at us and forces us to cover ourselves and wear warm

clothes to save ourselves. However, in the TL, the translator only depicts the literal side of the word and narrows it down to 'بوئے بنے کے شمال باد وہ' as if the wind performs the actions of human beings. The author goes on about the use of clothes and says that the clothes we wear reflect our inner self, and even though they hide our beauty – the natural state of the human body, they do not hide our ugliness.

Communicative Level:

In the context of the ST, the clothes are a representation of a different culture than the TL culture. When the broader meanings and relevance to culture is distorted in the TT, the meaning is lost and the culture changes from a broader perspective to a narrow one.

Conclusion

The culture in the excerpts of the selected poems, was analyzed on the basis of the lexical choices – the words, of the poet and the translator. It was evident from the analysis that the words choices of the poet were not random rather deliberate. And when these choices were replaced by translator's the meaning of the original got lost and the context of the TT completely changed. The words that had broader meaning or the deliberate metaphors that were used in the original were used to create a certain image of the cultural practices and items in the readers' minds. The poet wanted the readers to move beyond what they know in their cultures to how they can make it better. However, the translator's word choices mostly focused on transliteration by simply replacing SL words with TL ones and distorting the use of deliberate metaphors in the TT which resulted in the loss of meaning.

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